

**THE IMPACT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MORTGAGE-BACKED
SECURITIES MARKET ON THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY**

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the impact of the development of the mortgage-backed securities market on the country's economy. Key aspects of the mortgage market are considered, including its structure, regulatory mechanisms, and the role of mortgage-backed securities as a tool for raising capital. The paper analyzes how the development of this market can stimulate economic growth by increasing the affordability of housing, improving the financial stability of banks, and attracting investment. Examples from international practice are considered, and recommendations are offered for improving the mechanisms for regulating the mortgage market to ensure stability and sustainable economic development.

Keywords: mortgage-backed securities, mortgage-backed securities market, economic growth, financial stability, banking sector, investments, economic development, mortgage lending, financial instruments.

INTRODUCTION

The development of financial markets is an important factor determining the economic development of a country. One of the key elements of these markets is the mortgage-backed securities (MBS) market, which has a significant impact on the stability of the financial system and economic growth in general. Mortgage-backed securities serve as an important tool for raising capital, providing liquidity for banks and stimulating the housing market. In turn, the increased availability of mortgages contributes to an increase in the level of housing construction, which has a positive impact on the economy, creating new jobs and supporting demand for construction materials and services. However, as world practice has shown, excessive expansion of the mortgage market can carry significant risks, including an increase in the debt burden on households and the threat of financial crises. In particular, global financial crises, such as the crisis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The term "Mortgage" is of Greek origin. It was first used in a legal sense at the beginning of the 6th century BC by Solomon. A mortgage, or, literally, a stand, was a pillar that was installed on the debtor's boundary line with an inscription that this property serves as security for claims for a certain amount.¹

A mortgage loan is one of the forms of activity of financial institutions, which provides for the issuance of a long-term loan secured by real estate (The Mortgage Lending Scheme is given in Appendix 1). The very concept of a mortgage denotes a public pledge that guarantees the return of funds to the creditor.²

¹ Shchennikova L.V. Veshchnie prava v grajdanskom prave Rossii. – M., 1996. – S.64

² Gryaznova A.G. Otsenka nedvijimosti: ucheb. posobie. – M.: Finansi i statistika, 2014. – 496 s.

There are many definitions of “mortgage loan”. Below is a table that looks at several definitions developed by different researchers.

Table 1
Definitions of the term "mortgage loan"³

Source	Definition
Financial and Credit Encyclopedic Dictionary	a method of attracting financial resources in the form of loans secured by real estate ⁴
Balabanov I.T.	Pledge of real estate to secure a creditor's monetary claim ⁵
Lagutin V.D.	A mortgage loan is a special form of credit that is based on the provision of a loan secured by real estate. ⁶
Bazilevich V.D., Pogoreltseva N.B.	Relationships regarding the profitable movement of value in the area of real estate financing, provided as a long-term loan secured by land, other real estate or property rights, with the pledger retaining the right of ownership and use thereof, based on the basic principles of lending. ⁷
Razumova I.A.	A loan, an obligation, the repayment of which is secured by a pledge of real estate (mortgage). ⁸

Despite the fact that definitions of securitization of bank mortgage loans are expressed in foreign language literature (mainly English and Russian) differently (in exchange for different translation approaches), they are very close in content to each other. As an example, we can cite the term mortgage-backed securities (MBS) in English with an indication of various features of the corresponding translation into Russian. To date, the problem of asset securitization, including mortgages, has been most fully studied in the works of such economists as H. Baer, E. Davidson, E. Sanders, F. Fabozzi, T. Copeland, T. Koller, S. Gatti, A. Jobst, V.R. Jean Job, H. Lakhbir and others.

Asset backed securities are translated differently in many publications. For example, in Russian literature, translations such as “securities issued with collateral”, “securities issued with collateral in the form of financial assets”, “securities issued during securitization” may be used.⁹

Currently, the process of securitization is considered in a broad and narrow sense.¹⁰ In a broad sense, securitization is understood as the replacement of classical bank lending with financing based on the issue of securities. Securitization in a narrow sense, or asset securitization, is the process of transforming illiquid assets into liquid securities. The desire to increase the

³ The table was developed by the author.

⁴ Istochnik: <http://economics.niv.ru/doc/dictionary/financial-credit/articles/463/ipotechnyj-kredit.htm>

⁵ Banki i bankovskoe delo/ pod red. Balabanova. – SPb., 2005. – S.175

⁶ Lagutin V. D. Kreditovanie: teoriya i praktika / V.D. Lagutin. – K.: Znanie, 2007. – S.215

⁷ Bazilevich V.D. Ipotechniy rinok / V.D. Bazilevich, N.B. Pogoreltseva. – K.: Znaniya, 2008. – 717 s.

⁸ Razumova I. A. Ipotechnoe kreditovanie: Uchebnoe posobie / I. A. Razumova. – SPb.: Piter, 2006. – 208 s.

⁹ Endryu Devidson, Entoni Sanders, Len-Ling Volf, Anne Ching. Sekyuritizatsiya ipoteki: mirovoy opit, strukturirovanie i analiz/Per. s angl. O.V.Smorodinova pri uchastii V.Kachura.-M.: Vershina, 2007.-592 s.;

¹⁰ Xans Piter Ber. Sekyuritizatsiya aktivov: sekuyritizatsiya finansovix aktivov – innovatsionnaya texnika finansirovaniya bankov/Per. s nemetskogo Yu.M.Alekseeva, O.M.Ivanova. -M.: Volters Kluner, 2006.-624 s.

liquidity of assets leads to an increased role of securities in financial markets. Thus, securitization in a narrow sense is part of securitization in a broad sense (global securitization).

Securitized assets are described in different ways in different articles and literature. American academics argue that financial assets (such as mortgages, leases, and auto loan obligations) are the “raw material” for securitization. Some of these assets remain only as a transaction between two startups during their lifetime. Other types of assets are pooled together, consisting of many similar obligations that pass through several legal structures and can be sold to hundreds or thousands of investors in a pirated form.

Fig. 1. Comprehensive classification of US securitization market instruments¹¹

Securitization is the process of forming collections of financial obligations (pool) and providing them with forms that allow them to freely handle financial assets among the majority of investors. Securitization allows you to turn the initial set of obligations into a purchased (commercial) object. Fig. 1 shows that the main part of mortgage securities was the classic type of two-tier model of securitized mortgage assets - MBS. The share of secured mortgage obligations of CMOs in the market is significant, but is less than one third of the volume of MBS. The share of other types of mortgage securities do not exceed 10% of the total market volume.

Commercial papers are better insured against the risk of early repayment and offer two levels of protection:

- at the loan level and
- at the structural level.

The first level uses:

- a ban on early repayment (lockout prepayment),
- an agreement on the condition of liquidation of the debt (defeasance).¹²

¹¹ Developed by author on the basis of A. Litvintsev American securitization markets in 2018 / Encyclopedia of Russian securitization - 2019

¹² In which the borrower provides sufficient funds to create a portfolio of Treasury securities whose cash flow is identical to the cash flow of the loan in the absence of early repayment.

- these are prepayment penalty points,¹³
- this is a yield maintenance charge or a make-whole charge¹⁴,

There are currently four directions in the CMBS segment:

- Conduit - CMBS¹⁵
- SASB, (Single Asset/Single Borrower CMBS)¹⁶
- CRE CLO (Commercial Real Estate Collateralized Loan Obligation)¹⁷
- Agency CMBS¹⁸

RESULTS

In Uzbekistan, there are a number of legislative and by-laws that directly and indirectly regulate the relationships of business entities in the process of mortgage lending. The main ones are:

1. Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
2. Laws "On Pledge",
3. "On Property",
4. "On Mortgage",

A program is adopted annually to approve the volumes of construction of apartment buildings for mortgage lending in the republic. At the same time, tax legislation provides a number of tax benefits in order to ensure the effective functioning of the mortgage financing system and stimulate subjects of mortgage relations.

Based on the above regulations, in our studies of the features and distinctive features of the mortgage lending system in Uzbekistan, we defined its main elements and their interrelation; analyzed the characteristic features and current state of the national mortgage lending market; substantiated the main approaches to the transformation of the domestic mortgage lending model, taking into account international experience and the conditions of Uzbekistan.

The development of the mortgage-backed securities market in Uzbekistan in recent years has become an important element of economic policy aimed at stimulating housing construction, increasing the affordability of housing and improving the country's financial stability. An analysis of the impact of this market on the economy of Uzbekistan has shown both positive and potentially negative results.

One of the significant results of the development of the mortgage-backed securities market in Uzbekistan is the growth in housing affordability for the population. In recent years, there has been a steady increase in the volume of mortgage lending, which has become possible due to an increase in the volume of mortgage-backed securities issuance and improvement of the mechanisms for their circulation in the financial market. This, in turn, has increased the availability

¹³ A pre-determined penalty that a borrower wishing to refinance his debt must pay to the lender

¹⁴This makes it unprofitable for the borrower to refinance in order to obtain lower mortgage rates..

¹⁵ These are multi-borrower transactions. Frank J. Fabozzi Bond Market: Analysis and Strategies

¹⁶ The mortgage is a single loan on a hotel, office building or mall, or a portfolio of similar loans from the same borrower.

¹⁷ These are transactions that have a CLO structure (Russian: UZO, Collateralized loan obligations). There are fewer loans in such structures, about 30, and these are usually shorter loans taken to stabilize and renovate real estate.

¹⁸ These are multifamily housing securitization transactions guaranteed by mortgage agencies.

of housing for a wide range of the population, especially in large cities and centers of economic activity.

The development of the mortgage-backed securities market has contributed to attracting significant investment in the construction industry of Uzbekistan. MBS as investment instruments are becoming attractive to both local and international investors. Attracting private and institutional investors to the real estate and construction sector contributes not only to the growth of housing construction, but also to the creation of new jobs, which, in turn, has a positive effect on the economic growth of the country. The mortgage-backed securities market has played an important role in strengthening the financial system of Uzbekistan. Securitization of mortgage loans allows banks and financial institutions to improve liquidity and reduce the risks associated with asset concentration. This improves the financial stability of banks, stimulates lending and increases the volume of economic activity in the country.

Although the development of the mortgage market has contributed to the growth of housing affordability, it is also associated with an increase in the debt burden on the population. In the context of high interest rates and instability in the global markets for economic goods, some segments of the population may have difficulty servicing mortgage loans, which leads to an increase in overdue debt. In the event of a deterioration in the economic situation, this may affect the financial well-being of the population and lead to social instability.

Despite positive trends, the development of the mortgage-backed securities market in Uzbekistan is accompanied by a number of regulatory problems. At the moment, the country does not have a full-fledged and balanced regulatory system that could ensure the stability of this market in the long term. Risks associated with possible overheating of the mortgage market, rising housing costs and deterioration in the quality of mortgage loans may lead to financial crises similar to those that occurred in other countries in 2007-2008.

The mortgage-backed securities market in Uzbekistan is also subject to the influence of external economic factors. Changes in world prices for oil and natural resources, fluctuations in world interest rates, as well as economic instability in neighboring countries can affect the housing market and the stability of mortgage lending. In the context of global economic turbulence, these factors can create additional stress on the country's financial system and lead to financial difficulties for banks and borrowers.

To what extent does the mortgage market of Uzbekistan meet the requirements of the state's macroeconomic, including mortgage, policy?

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Fig. 1. Participants in the mortgage loan market

Fig. 1. shows that the bulk (95.6 percent) of mortgage loans are provided by local banks such as SQB (9.6%), IPTB (24.9%), NBU BRB (more than 17%) XALQ bank (12.8), which once again demonstrates the active participation of banks with a state share in the state social program to provide the population with housing.

The development of the mortgage securities market in Uzbekistan has significant potential for improving the availability of housing, attracting investment in the construction sector and strengthening the country's financial system. However, to minimize risks and ensure long-term stability of this market, it is necessary to pay attention to improving regulatory mechanisms, improving the financial literacy of the population and diversifying funding sources.

CONCLUSIONS

The main findings and results of the study are as follows:

- mortgage markets in world practice may differ in patterns and degrees, as well as other characteristics;
- since the secondary markets for securitization and mortgage loans differ in nature, ultimately leads to the same result;
- the market for existing mortgage-backed securities and related mortgage securities and securitization in the world can be conditionally divided into a single-level and two-stage model, a mixed model. In the two-stage model, both forms are used, securitization is carried out by state or non-state special operators (agencies or companies);
- the use of both models equally without fully taking into account the influence of existing fundamental factors in the country increases the likelihood of global crises;
- In Uzbekistan: a mortgage market has been formed, which, as in foreign countries, is mainly associated with the economy and state social, macroeconomic, including mortgage (housing) policy; an incomplete single-level (continental) model is in effect; the instrumental

structure of the mortgage market consists of the methods of the first form of mortgage relations and instruments; the institutional structure of the mortgage securities market has not yet been formed; the volume and growth dynamics of mortgage financing in Uzbekistan do not yet fully meet the requirements of the socio-economic policy of the state; the macroeconomic policy of the state has a strong influence on the development of the national mortgage market.

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